

Polyamine uptake transporter 2 is essential for systemic acquired resistance establishment in *Arabidopsis*

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ABSTRACT

The study of polyamine transport in plants has become increasingly important due to the central role of these amines in regulating growth, development, adaptation, and stress responses. This research focused on the *Arabidopsis thaliana* Polyamine Uptake Transporters gene family under conditions of systemic acquired resistance. We evaluated all single mutants of this gene family and found that the *put2-1* mutant abolished systemic acquired resistance while enhancing basal resistance to *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* DC3000. In contrast, the 35S::*PUT2* overexpression lines showed improved resistance and reduced bacterial titers compared to wild-type plants. RNA-seq analysis revealed that the *put2-1* mutant had deregulated expression of genes involved in the biosynthesis, signaling, and inactivation of salicylic acid and N-hydroxypipicolinic acid. Most of these genes were transcriptionally upregulated by putrescine in wild-type plants, but not in the *put2-1* mutant. Putrescine supplementation increased endogenous putrescine and salicylic acid levels in wild-type plants but not in *put2-1*, highlighting the essential role of this transporter in facilitating putrescine mobilization and regulating salicylic acid in distal tissues. We found that the defective systemic acquired resistance phenotype in the *put2-1* mutant was linked to changes in the timing of polyamines, ROS, phenolic compound accumulation, and alterations in stomatal immunity. Our study emphasizes the key role of the Polyamine Uptake Transporter 2 (*PUT2/LAT4*) in establishing systemic acquired resistance in *Arabidopsis*, while also maintaining the plant's intrinsic basal resistance mechanisms. These findings offer valuable insights into the complex mechanisms of plant resistance, positioning polyamine transport as a central hub in systemic responses.

1. Introduction

Plants have evolved a sophisticated and highly regulated immune system capable of responding rapidly to pathogen threats through mechanisms activated by pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs), producing a cascade of signals that culminate in PAMP-

triggered immunity (PTI). However, specific pathogens have adapted by deploying virulence factors known as effectors to suppress these innate immune responses. In response, plants have evolved the capacity to recognize these effectors through resistance proteins that activate effector-triggered immunity (ETI) (van der Burgh and Joosten, 2019).

Following the initial contact with a pathogen, plants fortify their

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local defenses and develop systemic acquired resistance (SAR), a state of heightened defensive readiness that confers long-lasting protection against a broad range of pathogens (Vlot et al., 2021). This systemic immunity is mediated by a complex network of signaling molecules like reactive oxygen species (ROS), Ca^{2+} , and "mobile signals" such as methyl salicylate (MeSA), azelaic acid (AzA), glycerol-3-phosphate (G3P), dehydroabietinal (DA), nitric oxide (NO), extracellular nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate [eNAD(P)] trans-acting siRNA-like RNAs (tasi-ARFs), and pinene monoterpenes (Guerra et al., 2020; Kachroo and Kachroo, 2020; Li et al., 2023; Vlot et al., 2021; Shine et al., 2022). SAR establishment leads to the production of salicylic acid (SA) and pipercolic acid (Pip), which facilitate communication between infected and distal tissues, effectively establishing an immune memory that primes the plant to respond more swiftly and robustly to subsequent infections (Lim, 2023).

Polyamines, aliphatic compounds with two or more amino groups, are usually protonated at physiological pH and play essential roles across a plant's life cycle, from embryogenesis and seed germination to fruit ripening and senescence (Blázquez, 2024). The most studied plant polyamines are the diamine putrescine (Put), the triamine spermidine (Spd), the tetraamines spermine (Spm), and thermospermine (tSpm) (Blázquez, 2024). However, their abundance depends on the plant species (Čavar Zeljković et al., 2024). Polyamines are crucial mediators of the plant defense response (Jiménez-Bremont et al., 2014; Gonzalez et al., 2021). For instance, their catabolism, particularly through the action of polyamine oxidases (PAO), generates hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), a reactive oxygen species (ROS) compound that inhibits pathogen growth, strengthens cell walls, induces stomata closure, and acts as a second messenger in the signaling network regulating defense gene expression (Wang et al., 2019). The *Atpao1-1 x Atpao2-1* double mutant, susceptible to *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* DC3000 (*Pst*), has altered ROS levels (Jasso-Robles et al., 2020). Contrarily, overexpression of apoplasmic *ZmPAO* in *Nicotiana tabacum* var. *Xanthi* increased tolerance to *P. syringae* pv. *tabaci* and the oomycete *Phytophthora parasitica* var. *nicotianae* (Moschou et al., 2009). Furthermore, endogenous Spm accumulation in *Arabidopsis thaliana* also confers resistance to *Pseudomonas viridiflava* (Gonzalez et al., 2011). However, polyamine catabolism is not always detrimental to pathogens, as the H_2O_2 produced by the *ZmPAO1* enzyme is essential for tumor development during the *Zea mays-Ustilago maydis* interaction, which favors pathogen survival (Jasso-Robles et al., 2016). The conjugation of polyamines with hydroxycinnamic acids produces compounds with antimicrobial activity. For instance, *p*-coumaroylputrescine bolsters the defense mechanisms of *A. thaliana* against the pathogen *Alternaria brassicicola* (Muroi et al., 2009).

While the intricate role of polyamine biosynthesis, conjugation, and catabolism in plant-pathogen interactions is partially known, our understanding of the implications of polyamine transport under stress conditions remains limited, especially regarding plant defense mechanisms. The *A. thaliana* genome encodes five genes for Polyamine Uptake Transporters (*PUT1-PUT5*), which belong to the L-type amino acid transporter (LAT) family of proteins. Structurally, these proteins have 10 to 12 transmembrane domains with cytoplasmic amino- and carboxy-terminal ends (Fujita and Shinozaki, 2014). In addition to polyamines, some PUT/LAT family members can transport amino acids (such as leucine), vitamin B1, and the herbicide paraquat (Mulangi et al., 2012; Li et al., 2013; Martinis et al., 2016; Begam and Good, 2017; Begam et al., 2020). The localization of PUTs in various cellular compartments, such as the endoplasmic reticulum (PUT1 and PUT5), Golgi apparatus (PUT2), chloroplast (PUT2 and PUT3), and plasma membrane (PUT3), suggests that these transporters play a significant role in the intracellular mobilization of polyamines in plants (Li et al., 2013; Fujita and Shinozaki, 2014; Ahmed et al., 2017).

Experimental evidence suggests that mobilizing plant polyamines under pathogen attack can promote plant resistance and, in some cases, pathogen virulence (Lowe-Power et al., 2018; Vilas et al., 2018). The

recent observation that Put or its derivatives could serve as a signaling molecule to activate ETI and SAR in *Arabidopsis*, particularly in a process largely dependent on H_2O_2 (Liu et al., 2020), leads us to hypothesize that the transport of polyamines or their derived metabolites via PUT/LAT transporters could significantly contribute to systemic defense responses. This study aimed to identify and functionally characterize PUT transporter(s) associated with SAR in *Arabidopsis*. Single mutants of the *PUT* gene family were assessed under SAR-inducing conditions to investigate how altered polyamine transport influences the plant's immune response, using the *Arabidopsis-Pseudomonas* pathosystem as a model. Using transcriptomic and metabolic approaches, we characterized the *put2-1* mutant to understand the basis of its SAR deficiency. Our findings provide key insights into the role of Put transport, highlighting its essential function in plant immunity.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Plant material and growth conditions

Arabidopsis thaliana ecotype Columbia-0 (WT) and T-DNA mutant lines for members of the polyamine uptake transporter family in *Arabidopsis* [*put1-1* (GABI_890c10), *put2-1* (SALK_119707c), *put3-1* (SALK_206472c), *put4-1* (SAIL_1275_c06), and *put5-1* (SALK_007135)] were acquired from Salk Institute Genomic Analysis Laboratory (www.signal.salk.edu/cgi-bin/tdnaexpress). Homozygous lines were identified by PCR. The absence of the *PUT* gene expression in the corresponding T-DNA mutant line was confirmed by qPCR (Fig. S1). Specific primers used for typing, cloning, and gene expression analysis are listed in Table S1.

For the experiments, seeds were stratified for 2 days in distilled water at 4 °C before being germinated in pots containing a sterile commercial substrate composed of sunshine#3: vermiculite: perlite (3:1:1). Plants were grown in a controlled growth chamber at 22 ± 2 °C under short-day photoperiod (8 h light/16 h dark) for 6 weeks for assessing bacterial titers in SAR conditions, transcriptomic and metabolomic analysis as described below. Additionally, plants were grown under a long-day photoperiod (16 h light/8 h dark regime) for 4 weeks to assess basal resistance.

2.2. Generation of the *AtPUT2* overexpression lines

The *AtPUT2* ORF sequence (1485 bp) was PCR amplified and cloned into the pENTER-D-TOPO entry vector (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) and recombined into the pEarley103 expression vector (Earley et al., 2006) using the Gateway LR clonase enzyme mix (Invitrogen). The expression clone (35S::*PUT2*) was transformed into *Rhizobium radiobacter* (formerly *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*) strain GV3101 by heat shock and then introduced into *A. thaliana* by floral dip. Transformed seeds were selected based on their resistance to glufosinate (Finale Ultra, BASF), following standard protocols (Harrison et al., 2006). Three independent overexpression lines were chosen for further analysis, 35S::*PUT2-2*, -18, and -27 (Fig. S1).

2.3. Bacterial strain and plant inoculation for SAR assays

Pseudomonas syringae pv. *tomato* DC3000 (*Pst*) and *Pseudomonas syringae* *avrRpt2* strains were used to induce SAR in *Arabidopsis* (Macho et al., 2010; Rufián et al., 2019). The strains were grown in King's B medium with rifampicin (50 µg/mL) at 28 °C. The SAR assay was carried out as Rufián et al. (2019) described. Briefly, the lower rosette leaves (8, 9, and 10) of six-week-old plants were inoculated with bacteria ($\text{OD}_{600}=0.005$) to induce local priming (SAR) or with the Mock (MgCl_2 10 mM, pH 7.0) as the control (native) condition. Then, 48 h after primary infection, upper leaves (13, 14, and 15) were systemically challenged with *Pst* ($\text{OD}_{600}=0.0005$). After a specific time, the upper leaves were collected for further analysis, assuming a native plant status or a

SAR condition has been established.

2.4. Polyamine infiltration for studying SAR-like responses

Validation experiments were conducted to elucidate further the role of specific polyamines in regulating SAR-like responses. For this, the lower leaves of six-week-old plants were infiltrated with 30 μ M Put, Spd, Spm or Mock. Then, 6 h after polyamine infiltration, the upper leaves were collected to quantify the gene expression of specific genes related to the SA and Pip pathways. Another set of plants, 48 h after Put infiltration, the upper leaves were challenged with *Pst* and collected at 72 h post-inoculation (hpi) for the estimation of bacterial titers. The upper leaves of Put-infiltrated plants were also collected at 6 and 24 h for further metabolic analysis.

2.5. Estimation of bacterial titers

Bacterial titers were determined in the upper leaves at 72 hpi. Six-leaf disks (\varnothing 0.5 cm) from each plant ($n = 5$) were homogenized in 0.2 mL of $MgCl_2$ (10 mM, pH 7.0) and serially diluted (1:10 to 1:1 $\times 10^9$). Then, 10 μ L of each dilution was plated on solid King's B agar supplemented with rifampicin (50 μ g/mL). Colony-forming units (CFU) were counted 24 h after incubation at 28 $^\circ$ C.

2.6. Fungal strain, spore collection, and plant inoculation

The *Botrytis cinerea* B05.10 strain was grown on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) for two weeks in the dark at 25 $^\circ$ C. The mycelium was scraped from the Petri dish, placed in a Tween 20 solution (0.02 %, v/v), filtered through a mesh, and centrifuged to obtain spores. After washing with sterile distilled water, the spores were resuspended in Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB) medium supplemented with sucrose (10 mM) and KH_2PO_4 (10 mM) and adjusted to a final concentration of 1×10^5 spores/mL.

For broad-spectrum SAR assays, six-week-old WT or *put2-1* mutant plants were locally primed with *Pst* ($OD_{600}=0.005$) or Mock (10 mM $MgCl_2$) on the lower leaves and then systemically challenged with *B. cinerea* by inoculating a drop (5 μ L) of spore suspension on the distal upper leaves. Inoculated leaves were collected at 24 and 48 hpi and stained with a 2.6 M Evans blue solution, following the protocol described by Vijayaraghavareddy et al. (2017). For tissue clarification, leaves were placed in an ethanol glycerol [90:10 (v/v)] solution and heated at 70 $^\circ$ C for 10 min or until no chlorophyll was visible. Clarified leaves were mounted on slides using a lactic acid:phenol:water [1:1:1 (v/v/v)] solution and photographed using a smartphone camera adapted to a stereoscope. Representative images were selected for each line and treatment, and lesion size was quantified using Image J Pro Plus 4.5 analysis software.

2.7. RNA isolation, Illumina sequencing, and data analysis

Total RNA was isolated using the TRI Reagent[®] method (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) following SAR assays. The lower leaves were inoculated with *Pst* to induce local priming (SAR) or Mock treatment. At 24 hpi, the uninoculated upper leaves were collected for RNA extraction. In a second group of plants, 48 h after primary infection, upper leaves were systemically challenged with *Pst* and collected at 24 hpi for RNA extraction (see Fig. 2a and b).

Three biological replicates, each containing over 20 μ g total RNA, were submitted to GENEWIZ[®] (<https://www.genewiz.com/>) for standard mRNA sequencing (by poly-A selection) using the Illumina HiSeq platform with a 2 \times 150 bp configuration. RNA-seq quality was analyzed using the FastQC v0.11.9 tool (Andrews, 2010), and the minimum read Phred score for the reads was 33. All reports from FastQC were collected using MultiQC v1.14. Neither adapter bias nor poor quality at the 3' end was evident in the RNA-seq data. There was no need to process the fragments. The Hisat2 v2.1.0 tool mapped the fastq files to the *Arabidopsis*

genome. R internal scripts were used for the Hisat2 mapping statistics process (R core team, 2022). The featureCounts tool from the SubRead package was used to quantify the mapped fragments (Liao et al., 2019). An internal R script (R core team, 2022) produced a counts matrix using these quantifications.

Differential expression analysis was performed using the *edgeR* R package (Robinson et al., 2010); the calcNormFactors function was used to calculate the normalization factors, and the estimatedDisp function was used with default parameters to calculate the dispersion. The *glmFit* function fits the data to the Negative Binomial density distribution. The *glmLRT* function defined and performed the proposed contrast between conditions. Differentially expressed genes were defined as those with a fold change value of ≥ 2 and a *p*-value ≤ 0.05 , and an FDR of ≤ 0.1 . Genes of interest with significant differential expression were validated by qPCR.

Gene Ontology (GO) term enrichment was performed using a custom R script with a logistic regression model. The *glm* function with the Binomial density distribution family and the *logit* link was used to fit the logistic regression model $y = f(x)$, defining the classes *y* as class 1-transcripts in the GO term and class 0-transcripts not in the GO term. The score *x* was defined as $x = -\log_{10}(\text{FDR})/\text{sign}(\log(\text{FC}))$.

The RNAseq data were deposited in the Gene Expression Omnibus database under the GEO accession GSE275478.

2.8. Gene expression analysis by RT-qPCR

Total isolated RNA was treated with DNase I (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA) to eliminate gDNA. First-strand cDNA synthesis was performed using the RevertAid Reverse Transcriptase Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). Gene expression levels were quantified by qPCR using the Maxima SYBR green qPCR Master Mix (2x) (Thermo Scientific). Primers used are listed in Table S1. qPCR thermal cycling conditions consisted of 30 s at 95 $^\circ$ C (initial denaturation), 40 PCR cycles of 10 s at 95 $^\circ$ C (denaturation), and 30 s at 60 $^\circ$ C (annealing/extension). Melting curves started at 65 $^\circ$ C and gradually increased the temperature every 0.5 $^\circ$ C up to 95 $^\circ$ C. The $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001) was used to calculate the change in gene expression relative to the control samples, with *AtEF1 α* (AT5G60390) as the reference gene.

2.9. Quantification of free polyamines

Six-week-old *Arabidopsis* plants were used to quantify the levels of free polyamines in the upper leaves after the different SAR treatments at 6 and 24 hpi. Briefly, lower leaves were inoculated with *Pst* to induce local priming (SAR) or Mock, and at 6 and 24 hpi the upper leaves were collected. In another set of plants, 48 h after the inoculation of the local leaves, the upper leaves were challenged with *Pst*, and samples were collected at 6 and 24 hpi. Leaves were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 $^\circ$ C. The samples were lyophilized, and the resulting dry weight (DW) was used for the targeted metabolic analysis.

Free polyamines were analyzed according to the method described by Čavar Zeljković et al. (2024). 200 μ L of 2 M NaOH was added to 200 μ L of the supernatant of the extract described above, followed by 2.5 μ L of benzoyl chloride in MeOH (50:50, v/v). The reaction mixture was vortexed for 5 s and then stirred for 40 min at 25 $^\circ$ C. After the reaction, 500 μ L of saturated NaCl was added, and benzoylated polyamines were extracted with 2 \times 500 μ L of diethyl ether. The solvent was evaporated under a vacuum at 40 $^\circ$ C. Dry samples were dissolved in 200 μ L of mobile phase and analyzed according to the protocol described by Čavar Zeljković et al. (2024), with minor modifications to include additional target compounds. The analysis was performed in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode, and transitions of the target compounds were as follows: Put (297.10>105.10, 297.10>77.05, 297.10>176.00), Dap (282.95>104.95, 282.95>77.00, 282.95>162.05), Dap-d₆ (288.95>112.95, 288.95>82.00, 288.95>170.05), Cad

(311.10>104.95, 311.10>77.05, 311.10>190.20), nSpd
 (444.15>105.05, 444.15>162.00, 444.15>322.20), Spd
 (458.20>105.10, 458.20>162.15, 458.20>336.30), hSpd
 (472.20>247.20, 472.20>105.05, 472.20>176.05), nSpm
 (605.00>162.20, 605.00>105.20, 605.00>323.30), tSpm
 (619.25>105.00, 619.25>162.00, 619.25>337.20), Spm
 (619.25>497.30, 619.25>162.00, 619.25>105.00), and Agm
 (443.00>104.85, 443.00>375.00).

2.10. Quantification of free phenolic compounds

Analysis of phenolic compounds was performed according to the protocol described in Sedláková et al. (2023). The UHPLC-MS/MS measurements were carried out on an Ultra Performance LC-MS 8050 system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) with a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in negative mode. A 5 µL sample was injected into an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column (1.7 µm, 2.1 × 100 mm, Waters, Milford, MA, USA), connected to the corresponding pre-column. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of 15 mM formic acid (pH 3, adjusted with NH₄OH) (solvent A) and ACN (solvent B) at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. The linear gradient consisted of 10 % B for 1 min, 10–13 % B for 2 min, isocratic 13 % B for 4 min, 13–25 % B for 3 min, 25–70 % B for 1.2 min, isocratic 75 % B for 0.8 min, back to 10 % B within 0.5 min, and equilibration for 3.5 min. The analysis was performed in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode, and transitions of the target compounds were as follows: SAG (297.70>137.10, 297.70>93.10), pCA-d₆ (169.10>124.85, 169.10>97.15, 169.10>98.10), pCA (163.00>119.10, 163.00>93.00, 163.00>117.10), SiA (227.70>208.30, 222.70>192.20, 222.70>164.30), FA (193.10>134.25, 193.10>178.25), SA-d₄ (141.10>96.80, 141.10>69.10, 141.10>78.10), and SA (137.10>92.70, 137.10>65.00, 137.10>75.05). All standards and reagents were of the highest available purity and purchased from Sigma Aldrich Company (Prague, Czech Republic).

2.11. Stomatal aperture analysis

The stomatal aperture was assessed following Pantaleno et al. (2024). Epidermal peels were obtained from the abaxial side of leaves from six-week-old plants and placed in the opening buffer (5 mM MES, pH 6.1, 50 mM KCl) for 3 h under light to encourage the optimal opening of most stomata. Then, the peels were treated with or without 1 µM flagellin 22 (flg22) for 0-, 15-, 30-, and 60-min periods. Stomata were observed under a microscope using a 40x objective and documented with a digital camera. The stomatal aperture was analyzed by Image J Pro Plus 4.5 analysis software.

2.12. Luminol assay

Luminol assays were conducted as outlined Biscaglia et al. (2015) with minor modifications. The lower leaves of six-week-old plants were infiltrated with Mock or *Pst* (as described above) to induce local priming, and the upper leaves were used for the luminol assay. Discs were obtained from the midrib level using a sharp 4 mm biopsy punch from at least three leaves per plant and carefully transferred to a Petri dish containing ddH₂O. Using a flat toothpick, one leaf disc was placed in each well of a 96-well luminometer plate, containing 150 µL ddH₂O with the adaxial side facing upward. To minimize the impact of wounding, the plates were kept under the same growth conditions as the original plants for 20 h. Before measurement, water was removed from each well, and 100 µL of reaction solution (100 µM luminol, 10 µg/mL horseradish peroxidase, and 1 µM flg22) was added. Luminescence of the disc reaction mixture without the elicitor was monitored as the blank. Luminol luminescence was measured for one hour using the multimode reader Synergy H4 from BioTek, at 2-min intervals with an integration time of 1000 ms.

2.13. Statistical analysis

The results of each representative experiment are shown as the mean ± SE. Statistical differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were determined by Student's t-test using GraphPad Prism version 10.0.0; by Generalized Linear Mixed Models (GLMMs) with negative binomial distribution or by two-way, three-way, or four-way ANOVA with LSD Fisher comparison as appropriate using the InfoStat v2020e (<https://www.infostat.com.ar/index.php?mod=page&id=15>) statistical package. Graphs were obtained using GraphPad Prism version 10.0.0. Asterisks and different letters indicate statistically significant differences between the means.

The changes in the metabolic profile between lines and treatments were also analyzed using multivariate statistical analysis, specifically principal component analysis (PCA) and correlation matrices performed in RStudio (Version 1.1.463 – © 2009–2018 RStudio, Inc.) using the packages *factoextra*, *ggplot2*, *grid*, *ggrepel*, *ggnewscale* and *corplot*.

3. Results

3.1. The AtPUT2 polyamine uptake transporter is essential for SAR establishment but not for basal resistance in *Arabidopsis*

SAR was induced in WT plants and single mutant lines of the *A. thaliana* PUT family (*put1-1*, *put2-1*, *put3-1*, *put4-1*, and *put5-1*). CFUs were estimated at 72 hpi following systemic challenge with *Pst* in six-week-old plants. In WT plants, bacterial titers were significantly lower in systemic leaves of locally challenged (primed) compared to the Mock-treated controls, indicating successful SAR establishment, as reported in previous studies (Rufián et al., 2019). We first analyzed bacterial titers in WT and mutant lines after Mock-infiltration. The *put1-1* behaved like WT, while the other mutants increased basal resistance (Fig. 1a). Under SAR-induced conditions, *put1-1* and *put3-1* mutants reduced bacterial titers after priming as the WT (Fig. 1a). In contrast, the *put2-1*, *put4-1*, and *put5-1* mutant lines displayed a defective SAR. Notably, *put4-1* and *put5-1* mutants showed similar bacterial titers in primed plants as in the Mock-infiltrated ones (Fig. 1a).

The *put2-1* mutant exhibited the most pronounced SAR deficiency, with higher bacterial titers in primed plants than in the Mock-infiltrated ones, suggesting a key role for AtPUT2 in SAR (Fig. 1a). To further study the role of AtPUT2 in SAR, we generated three *Arabidopsis* PUT2 overexpression lines (*35S::PUT2-2*, *-18*, and *-27*) and challenged them with *Pst*. All *35S::PUT2* overexpression lines were resistant to *Pst* inoculation, inducing SAR, and exhibited similar bacterial titers to the WT (Fig. 1a).

Following inoculation with the avirulent strain *P. syringae* *avrRpt2*, the *put2-1* mutant failed to establish SAR, as evidenced by increased bacterial titers compared to the native plant status (Fig. 1b). Interestingly, the *put2-1* mutant line also exhibited enhanced basal resistance (Fig. 1a and b). Specifically, *put2-1* plants inoculated with the Mock on the lower leaves and challenged on the upper leaves with *Pst* had lower bacterial titers than WT, a phenotype consistent even in four-week-old *put2-1* mutant plants (Fig. S2). This suggests a dual phenotype for the *put2-1* mutant, in which SAR is compromised, but basal resistance is enhanced.

3.2. Broad-spectrum SAR is lost in the *Arabidopsis* *put2-1* mutant

SAR provides broad-spectrum protection against various pathogens. We examined whether AtPUT2 influences this protection by testing SAR induced by *Pst* against an unrelated pathogen, *Botrytis cinerea*, in the WT and the *put2-1* mutant line (Fig. 1c and d). Plants in native or SAR status were systemically inoculated with *B. cinerea*, and the infected leaves were stained with Evans blue. In WT plants, local priming with *Pst* significantly reduced lesion sizes caused by *B. cinerea* at 48 hpi, demonstrating effective broad-spectrum SAR (Fig. 1c). However, the *put2-1* mutant showed larger fungal lesions in *Pst*-primed plants (Fig. 1c and d), indicating impaired broad-spectrum SAR. This result suggests

Fig. 1. Evaluation of SAR and broad-spectrum SAR in *Arabidopsis* polyamine uptake transporter mutants and overexpression lines. a) Bacterial titers in systemic leaves of WT and polyamine uptake transporter mutants (*put1-1*, *put2-1*, *put3-1*, *put4-1*, and *put5-1*) and *AtPUT2* overexpression lines (*35S::PUT2-2*, *-18*, and *-27*) which were locally infiltrated with Mock, maintaining a native plant status, or challenged with *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* DC3000 (*Pst*) to induce SAR. b) Bacterial titers in systemic leaves of WT and *put2-1*. Plants were locally infiltrated with Mock or challenged with the avirulent strain *P. syringae avrRpt2*. CFU, colony-forming units. Experiments were repeated twice with similar results. Values show the mean of five or six biological replicates \pm SE. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments according to two-way ANOVA and LSD Fisher's post-hoc test. c) Lesion size in WT and *put2-1* mutant plants, locally infiltrated with Mock or challenged with *Pst*, was assessed in systemic leaves after inoculation with *B. cinerea* (*Bc*). Values are the mean of four biological replicates ($n = 12$ leaves) \pm SE. Lesion size (cm^2) induced by *Bc* was quantified using ImageJ® software. Different letters denote significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments via three-way ANOVA followed by LSD Fisher's post-hoc test. d) Evans blue staining at 24 and 48 hpi with *Bc*. Representative image of 12 leaves. Scale bar (0.5 cm). Each image displays a 2x digital zoom.

that while the loss of *AtPUT2* function does not affect basal resistance to *Pst* in *Arabidopsis*, this transporter is crucial for managing SAR, even against unrelated pathogens.

3.3. Transcriptomic profiling reveals that the *put2-1* mutant exhibits altered expression of genes associated with defense and SAR

To further investigate the role of the *AtPUT2* gene in plant defense, we conducted a transcriptome analysis of WT and *put2-1* mutant plants

under native and SAR conditions at 24 hpi (Fig. 2a and b; complete gene list available at File S1). For the native condition, the lower leaves of a set of plants were infiltrated with Mock solution, while the upper leaves were either kept in their native state or challenged with *Pst* (Fig. 2a). For the SAR condition, the lower leaves were infiltrated with *Pst*, while the upper leaves were either maintained in their native state or challenged

with *Pst* (Fig. 2a). Samples were collected at 24 hpi as indicated (Fig. 2b). RNA-seq analysis revealed 28.8 ± 2.1 million fragments per library with high quality (minimum Phred score of 33) (Fig. S3). In the considered comparisons, 1160 genes showed increased gene expression, and 3857 showed decreased expression (Fig. 2c and d). In the *put2-1* mutant, the comparison of SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$) vs. native ($1^{\circ}Mock / 2^{\circ}Pst$) had

Fig. 2. Transcriptomic analysis of *put2-1* mutant under native and SAR conditions.

a) Experimental design and b) sampling. WT and *put2-1* plants were inoculated with *Pst* to establish the following conditions: native plant status and SAR. The lower leaves (8, 9, and 10) were inoculated with *Pst* at $OD_{600} = 0.005$ to induce local priming (SAR) or treated with a Mock solution ($MgCl_2$ 10 mM) to maintain a native plant status. At 24 hpi, the uninoculated upper leaves (13, 14, and 15) were collected for RNA extraction. In a second group of plants, 48 h after primary infection, the upper leaves were systemically challenged with *Pst* at $OD_{600} = 0.0005$ and then collected 24 hpi for RNA extraction. For each condition, at least six plants were used. Scissors indicate the upper leaves that were harvested for the experiments. Venn diagrams representing the common and specific number of c) upregulated genes and d) down-regulated genes between the considered contrasts. e) Heatmap summarizing the Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment for selected terms based on the contrasts. The scale color represents the enrichment score.

the highest number of differentially expressed genes (DE), with 1107 increased and 3811 decreased (Fig. 2c and d). Furthermore, there were only 9 genes with increased and 3 with reduced expression shared between *put2-1* [SAR (^{1°Pst} / ^{2°Pst}) vs. native (^{1°Mock} / ^{2°Pst})] and WT [SAR (^{1°Pst} / ^{2°Native}) vs. native (^{1°Mock} / ^{2°Native})] conditions (Table S2).

Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis, based on the Differential Expression results, revealed deregulated terms associated with SAR (GO:0009627), response to hydrogen peroxide (GO:0042542), regulation of defense response (GO:0031347), response to fungus (GO:0009620), plant-type hypersensitive response (GO:0009626), fatty acid biosynthetic process (GO:0006633), thylakoid membrane organization (GO:0010027) and plant-type cell wall organization (GO:0009664) in the *put2-1* mutant compared to WT (Fig. S4). A heatmap summarizing the GO enrichment analysis of all contrasts is shown in Fig. 2e. Representative deregulated genes associated with SAR and defense in *put2-1* under SAR (^{1°Pst} / ^{2°Pst}) condition are listed in Table 1, with many linked to SA and Pip metabolism.

3.4. The *put2-1* mutant displays deregulation in the SA and SAR marker genes

Expression of SAR and defense marker genes was evaluated in the upper (systemic) leaves of the WT and *put2-1* plants under native or SAR

conditions (Fig. 3). The key examined genes included: SA synthesis and response (*PAD4*, *SARD1*, *ICS1*, and *PR1*), Pip and NHP biosynthesis (*ALD1*, *SARD4*, and *FMO1*), SAR signaling (*AZ11*), negative regulation of *NPR1* (*NIMIN1*), glycosylation of NHP and SA (*UGT76B1*), the ethylene- and jasmonate-responsive plant defensin (*PDF1.2*) and a Spm responsive gene (*NHL10*) (Fig. 3). The expression of most genes was influenced by the interaction among local priming, systemic challenge and genotype according to ANOVA (File S2). Under native (^{1°Mock} / ^{2°Native}) conditions, *put2-1* exhibited increased expression of most genes related to SA synthesis and response (*PAD4*, *SARD1*, *ICS1*, *PR1*), Pip, and NHP biosynthesis (*ALD1* and *FMO1*), as well as *AZ11* and *PDF1.2* compared to WT (Fig. 3a-e, g, j and k), consistent with its basal resistance phenotype (Fig. 1a). After local priming with *Pst* (^{1°Pst} / ^{2°Native}), expression of these marker genes showed slight changes in WT plants regarding the native uninoculated (^{1°Mock} / ^{2°Native}) condition (Fig. 3). At the same time, *put2-1* increased the expression of *PAD4*, *SARD4*, *NIMIN1*, *UGT76B1*, *AZ11*, and *NHL10* (Fig. 3a, f, h-j, and l), but decreased *PR1*, *ALD1*, and *FMO1*, as well as *PDF1.2* (Fig. 3d, e, g and k), compared to the native uninoculated condition.

In systemically challenged plants without priming (^{1°Mock} / ^{2°Pst}), both WT and *put2-1* upregulated most marker genes, particularly *SARD1* and *PR1* in the mutant (Fig. 3b and d). Interestingly, genes related to SA and NHP biosynthesis (*SARD1*, *ICS1*, *SARD4*, and *FMO1*), as well as the *PR1*

Table 1
Up and down-regulated genes in the *put2-1* mutant in the SAR (^{1°Pst} / ^{2°Pst}) vs. native (^{1°Mock} / ^{2°Pst}) comparison.

GeneID	Description	Involved process	logFC	p value	FDR
AT3G30775	Early responsive to dehydration 5 (ERD5)	Defense	5.237	7.10E-13	2.22E-10
AT5G42380	Calmodulin like 37 (CML37)	Defense	4.262	6.11E-06	1.11E-04
AT2G19190	FLG22-induced receptor-like kinase 1 (FRK1)	Defense	3.451	1.23E-02	4.74E-02
AT3G22600	Glycosylphosphatidylinositol-anchored lipid protein transfer 5 (LTPG5)	Defense	3.244	4.17E-03	2.02E-02
AT3G23250	MYB domain protein 15 (MYB15)	Defense	3.137	6.26E-03	2.79E-02
AT1G19020	Small defense-associated protein 1 (SDA1)	Defense	3.046	1.28E-06	3.12E-05
AT1G22890	PROSCOOP14	Defense	3.017	1.75E-07	6.07E-06
AT2G39660	Botrytis-induced kinase 1 (BIK1)	Defense	2.865	2.25E-07	7.41E-06
AT1G74710	Isochorismate synthase 1 (ICS1)	Defense	2.854	3.49E-06	6.98E-05
AT1G28330	Dormancy-associated protein 1 (DYL1)	Defense	2.552	8.07E-04	5.54E-03
AT4G23810	WRKY transcription factor 53 (WRKY53)	Defense	2.203	9.64E-03	3.92E-02
AT2G43790	Mitogen-activated protein kinase 6 (MPK6)	Defense	1.326	3.04E-05	4.02E-04
AT1G64280	Nonexpressor of pathogenesis-related genes 1 (NPR1)	Defense	1.017	4.21E-03	2.03E-02
AT5G44420	Plant defensin 1.2 (PDF1.2)	Defense	-3.509	1.21E-03	7.68E-03
AT5G05300	Peptide IDL6	Defense*	3.788	1.17E-07	4.39E-06
AT5G05190	Enhanced disease resistance 4 (EDR4)	Defense*	2.863	1.42E-09	1.05E-07
AT3G52400	Syntaxin of plants 122 (SYP122)	Defense*	2.667	1.34E-05	2.08E-04
AT2G39030	L-ornithine N5-acetyltransferase (NATA1)	Defense*	-2.646	7.70E-03	3.28E-02
AT1G16420	Metacaspase-8 (MC8)	HR	3.263	1.14E-02	4.46E-02
AT1G66090	Disease resistance protein (TIR-NBS class)	HR	3.177	7.42E-07	1.98E-05
AT4G25110	Metacaspase-2 (MC2)	HR	3.141	3.32E-05	4.33E-04
AT3G01290	Hypersensitive induced reaction 2 (HIR2)	HR	2.702	3.30E-04	2.72E-03
AT2G45170	Autophagy-related protein 8e (ATG8E)	HR	2.547	1.86E-05	2.72E-04
AT4G12720	Nudix hydrolase homolog 7 (NUDT7)	ROS	2.677	7.92E-08	3.21E-06
AT2G13810	AGD2-like defense response protein 1 (ALD1)	SAR	6.227	2.21E-05	3.11E-04
AT1G19250	Flavin dependent monooxygenase 1 (FMO1)	SAR	5.157	2.94E-03	1.54E-02
AT4G12470	Azelaic acid induced 1 (AZI1)	SAR	5.024	9.27E-06	1.57E-04
AT4G12480	Early Arabidopsis aluminum induced 1 (EARL11)	SAR	3.820	4.39E-05	5.44E-04
AT2G35980	NDR1/HIN1-like protein 10 (NHL10)	SAR	3.711	5.49E-03	2.52E-02
AT1G73805	SAR deficient 1 (SARD1)	SAR	2.508	8.16E-04	5.59E-03
AT5G26920	CAM-binding protein 60-like G (CBP60G)	SAR	2.349	7.67E-03	3.27E-02
AT5G52810	SAR deficient 4 (SARD4)	SAR	2.338	1.45E-05	2.21E-04
AT4G33430	BRI1-associated receptor kinase 1 (BAK1)	SAR	1.977	3.06E-08	1.44E-06
AT3G52430	Phytoalexin deficient 4 (PAD4)	SAR	1.575	1.23E-04	1.23E-03
AT1G80460	Nonhost resistance to P. S. Phaseolicola 1 (NH01)	SAR	1.312	5.32E-03	2.45E-02
AT5G14760	Flagellin-insensitive 4 (FIN4)	SAR	1.092	1.16E-02	4.52E-02
AT4G31780	Monogalactosyl diacylglycerol synthase 1 (MGD1)	SAR	-1.058	4.17E-03	2.02E-02
AT4G27030	Fatty acid desaturase 4 (FAD4)	SAR	-1.263	2.20E-02	7.40E-02
AT3G11170	Fatty acid desaturase 7 (FAD7)	SAR	-1.418	2.66E-04	2.29E-03
AT2G40690	Suppressor of fatty acid desaturase deficiency 1 (SFD1 or GLY1)	SAR	-1.565	6.51E-04	4.65E-03
AT2G05990	Mosaic death 1 (MOD1)	SAR	-2.403	3.63E-04	2.94E-03
AT1G49430	Long-chain acyl-CoA synthetase 2 (LACS2)	SAR	-3.575	6.30E-06	8.34E-09
AT1G02450	NIM1-interacting 1 (NIMIN1)	SAR*	4.966	1.12E-06	2.79E-05
AT3G25882	NIM1-interacting 2 (NIMIN2)	SAR*	4.434	1.39E-10	1.55E-08
AT3G11340	UDP-glycosyltransferase 76B1	SAR*	3.646	1.58E-02	5.73E-02

* Asterisks indicate a negative role in the respective process.

Fig. 3. Gene expression analysis of SAR markers in the *put2-1* mutant line. Gene expression of a) *PAD4*, b) *SARD1*, c) *ICS1*, d) *PRI*, e) *ALD1*, f) *SARD4*, g) *FMO1*, h) *NIMIN1*, i) *UGT76B1*, j) *AZI1*, k) *PDF1.2*, and l) *NHL10* in the different plant status (native or SAR) at 24 hpi. Gene expression values were normalized to the *EF1α* reference gene and relative to WT plants in native status ($1^{\circ}\text{Mock} / 2^{\circ}\text{Native}$) using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$ method. Values are the mean of three replicates \pm SE. Different letters denote significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments according to three-way ANOVA and LSD Fisher's post-hoc test.

gene, showed higher expression in the *put2-1* mutant compared to WT under the locally primed and systemically challenged ($1^{\circ}\text{Pst} / 2^{\circ}\text{Pst}$) condition (Fig. 3b, c, f, and g). In the same conditions, negative regulators (*NIMIN1* and *UGT76B1*) and *NHL10* were strongly induced in *put2-1* compared to WT (Fig. 3h, i, and l). Notably, *NIMIN1*, *UGT76B1*, and *NHL10* displayed a consistent expression pattern in *put2-1* across all tested conditions, differing markedly from WT (Fig. 3h, i, and l). Overall, the simultaneous strong induction of both positive and negative SAR regulators in *put2-1* likely disrupts the balance between induction and

attenuation of SAR, leading to an impaired systemic response.

The stronger expression of SA and SAR marker genes in *put2-1* under SAR ($1^{\circ}\text{Pst} / 2^{\circ}\text{Pst}$) condition compared to WT suggested a delayed response to secondary infection. To test this, we examined the expression of SAR-related genes (*ICS1*, *PRI*, *FMO1*, *SARD4*, *NHL10*, and *UGT76B1*) at an earlier time point (6 hpi) (Fig. S5). ANOVA revealed that, except for *ICS1*, the expression of all genes was influenced by the interaction among local priming, systemic challenge, and genotype (File S2). Our results confirmed that the WT responded more rapidly to systemic

challenge without priming ($1^{\circ}\text{Mock} / 2^{\circ}\text{Pst}$), whereas *put2-1* exhibited a delayed response (Fig. S5). The exception was *SARD4*, which behaved similarly in both lines (Fig. S5c). Interestingly, in the SAR and systemically challenged condition ($1^{\circ}\text{Pst} / 2^{\circ}\text{Pst}$), most analyzed genes were less expressed in WT than in *put2-1*, except for *PR1* and *UGT76B1*. In WT, priming likely triggers a rapid response after the challenge of systemic leaves with *Pst*, and by 6 hpi, the expression levels of marker genes may have already decreased. This suggests that plant status differentially affects gene expression in the WT and the *put2-1* mutant.

3.5. AtPUT2 is crucial for the proper expression of SAR marker genes relying on putrescine

To investigate the role of free polyamines and their transport in SAR, we locally infiltrated the lower leaves of six-week-old WT and *put2-1* mutant plants with Mock (MgCl_2) or 30 μM of selected polyamines (Put, Spd, Spm). Then, we measured the expression of SAR marker genes in the upper leaves at 24 hpi. ANOVA revealed that the interaction between polyamine type and genotype influenced gene expression (File S2). In WT, Put treatment significantly increased the expression of all marker genes, but the systemic effect of Put was impaired in the *put2-1* mutant (Fig. 4). Spd strongly induced *PR1*, *SARD4*, *FMO1*, and *NIMIN1* expression in WT, but had little effect on the other marker genes

analyzed (Fig. 4b-d, and h). In *put2-1*, Spd treatment reduced marker gene expression (Fig. 4). Finally, Spm increased the expression of negative regulators of SAR (*UGT76B1* and *NIMIN1*) in *put2-1*, and to a lesser extent, *UGT76B1* expression in WT (Fig. 4e and h). These results align with previous findings that local Put treatment triggers a SAR-like response in *Arabidopsis* (Liu et al., 2020), and demonstrate the crucial role of the AtPUT2 transporter for relaying systemic signal(s) to distal leaves for proper SAR gene expression.

3.6. Local infiltration of Put results in a reduction of bacterial titers in systemic tissues

Since Put infiltration triggered the expression of SAR marker genes, we evaluated its impact on *Pst* systemic resistance. Six-week-old WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2* overexpression lines were locally infiltrated with 30 μM Put or Mock, followed by *Pst* inoculation of the upper leaves 48 h later. At 72 hpi, Put-treated WT plants showed significantly lower bacterial titers than the Mock-treated plants, indicating SAR activation (Fig. 5). Conversely, the *put2-1* consistently maintained low bacterial titers, with no significant differences between Mock and Put treatments (Fig. 5). Interestingly, the *35S::PUT2* overexpression lines exhibited low bacterial titers even in the Mock-treated plants, similar to the *put2-1* mutant, suggesting basal resistance. Furthermore, the *35S::PUT2* lines

Fig. 4. Regulation of SAR marker genes by polyamines. Gene expression of a) *ICS1*, b) *PR1*, c) *SARD4*, d) *FMO1*, e) *UGT76B1*, f) *AZI1*, g) *NHL10*, and h) *NIMIN1* in systemic leaves at 6 h after local infiltration with Mock or 30 μM Put, Spd, or Spm. Gene expression values were normalized to the *EF1 α* reference gene and relative to WT Mock plants using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$ method. Values are the mean of three replicates \pm SE. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments according to two-way ANOVA and LSD Fisher's post-hoc test.

Fig. 5. Bacterial titers in distal leaves following the infiltration of Put in local leaves. Bacterial titers were assessed in distal leaves of the WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2* overexpression lines at 48 h after infiltrating lower leaves with either Mock, *Pst* priming, or 30 μ M Put. CFU, colony-forming units. The experiments were repeated twice, yielding consistent results. The values represent the mean of five biological replicates \pm SE. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) among Mock, *Pst* priming, or Put treatment in the WT, *put2-1* mutant, and *35S::PUT2* overexpression lines, according to a GLMM with negative binomial distribution followed by LSD Fisher's post-hoc test.

had enhanced systemic resistance under Put treatment (Fig. 5). These results indicate that Put or its derived metabolites trigger SAR induction in the WT plants (Fig. 5). Although Put is a less preferred substrate for PUT2 in yeast expression assays (Mulangi et al., 2012), our findings suggest that *in planta*, PUT2 play a role in Put transport that is crucial for conferring systemic resistance to *Pst*.

3.7. The *put2-1* mutant line is affected in the Put mobilization

As previously observed, Put infiltration upregulated the expression of SAR marker genes and a SAR-like phenotype in the WT, but not in *put2-1*, which aligns with the defective Put transport in this mutant line. Therefore, we assessed the effect of local infiltration with 30 μ M Put on the content of free polyamines in distal leaves at 6- and 24-h post-infiltration (Fig. 6). A significant interaction was found among genotype, treatment, and time (File S2). In the WT, a notable increase in endogenous Put levels was detected in the distal leaves 6 h after Put infiltration of lower leaves, compared to the Mock treatment (Fig. 6b). This result demonstrates active mobilization of Put from lower to upper leaves. At this time, PCA also showed that Put and Spd were rapidly accumulated in the Put-infiltrated WT (Fig. 6b, c, and e). Contrary, following Put infiltration, *put2-1* exhibited either decreased (6 h) or unchanged (24 h) Put content in systemic leaves (Fig. 6b), indicating impaired Put mobilization from lower to upper leaves. Interestingly, the *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line behaved similarly to WT, increasing the endogenous Put content at 6 and 24 h after Put infiltration (Fig. 6b). Moreover, this line also rapidly accumulated other superior polyamines, such as Spm and tSpm, among others, but reduced their levels at 24 h, as happened in the WT (Fig. 6e; Fig. S6). These results may suggest that the Put fast transport is needed for the synthesis of the superior polyamines to regulate *Arabidopsis* SAR-induced response against *Pst*. This assumption was then further supported by the changes observed in the Put precursor Agm, which reduced in *put2-1* at 6 h and increased at 24 h, perhaps as a compensation response in the distal leaves for the Put reduced transport (Fig. 6a). In this regard, PC analysis indicated that in the *put2-1* mutant, Put infiltration induced Cad at 6 h, but didn't accumulate the higher polyamines until 24 h after the treatment (Fig. 6e).

3.8. Putrescine modulates SA levels in distal tissues

As described in previous sections, the *put2-1* mutant upregulated SA and SAR marker genes under native conditions (Fig. 3, Fig. S5), suggesting a deregulation of endogenous SA content. Therefore, a deeper analysis of phenolic compounds, including SA and SA-glucoside (SAG), was performed in the distal leaves of plants at 6 and 24 h after Put infiltration (Fig. 7). The Mock-treated *put2-1* mutant exhibited higher SA content than the WT at 6 h (Fig. 7a). Following Put infiltration, the WT distal leaves showed a significant increase in SA levels at 6 h, which remained at 24 h (Fig. 7a). These results suggest that Put translocation to distal tissues may regulate SA levels in the WT. In contrast, *put2-1* displayed delayed SA accumulation, which only increased after 24 h, implying impaired Put-mediated systemic signaling (Fig. 7a and 7f). The *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line maintained elevated SA levels both with and without Put treatment (Fig. 7a), a feature also observed in the PCA analysis (Fig. 7f).

Put infiltration in the local leaves also influenced the SAG content of the distal leaves (Fig. 7b). For instance, the WT accumulated significantly higher SAG levels in Put-infiltrated plants at 24 h, most likely to regulate SA levels that were significantly increased at 6 h (Fig. 7a, b, and f). Similarly, the *put2-1* mutant enhanced SAG content at 24 h after Put infiltration (Fig. 7b). In contrast, the *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line significantly raised SAG levels from 6 h after Put infiltration and kept them elevated at 24 h (Fig. 7b and f). Altogether, the data demonstrate that local Put infiltration and its transport via *AtPUT2* impact SA and SAG levels in systemic leaves. Furthermore, Put infiltration also modified the endogenous content of other phenolic compounds, including hydroxycinnamic acids, such as sinapic (SiA), ferulic (FA), and *p*-coumaric acid (pCA) (Fig. 7c-e). Although no clear regulation of Put infiltration was observed regarding the changes of these last phenolic compounds, it was clear that *AtPUT2* modulation may contribute to regulating the levels of SiA, which significantly increased in the WT at 6 h after Put infiltration, but not in *put2-1* and *35S::PUT2-27* lines (Fig. 7c).

3.9. The *put2-1* SAR deficiency is due to its disrupted polyamine homeostasis

We also measured the same aforementioned polyamines and phenolic compounds in the WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2-27* to understand the metabolic alterations due to *AtPUT2* disruption under SAR conditions (Fig. 8; Fig. S7). Significant differences were observed between the WT and the *put2-1* plants, while the *35S::PUT2-27* line behaved similarly to WT (Fig. 8; File S2). At 6 hpi under native conditions (1° Mock / 2° Mock), the *put2-1* mutant had increased content of several higher polyamines [Spd, hSpd, norspermidine (nSpd), Spm, tSpm, norspermine (nSpm)], as well as Cad and 1,3-diaminopropane (Dap), compared to the WT (Fig. 8b; Fig. S7). The *put2-1* mutant maintained increased levels of nSpd, Spm, nSpm, and tSpm at 24 hpi in native conditions, which align with the higher *ADC*, *SPMS*, and *ACL5* expression levels in this mutant (Fig. 8 g; Fig. S7 and S8). Interestingly, there was a clear negative correlation between Put and Spd and other polyamines like hSpd, Spm, tSpm, nSpd, and nSpm at 6 hpi (Fig. 8f). Maybe, the Put deficiency in *put2-1* is not only due to the limited Put transport but also rapid Spd conversion into the final product, such as Spm and tSpm, among others, which would condition the SAR. As a corroboration, *put2-1* reduced the Put content under SAR (1° Pst / 2° Pst) at 6 hpi (Fig. 8a). Contrarily, the WT and *35S::PUT2-27* accumulated higher polyamines and Dap under SAR (1° Pst / 2° Pst), whereas the *put2-1* mutant showed a correlation with phenolics, including SiA, SA, and SAG (Fig. 8c, d, e; Fig. S7). The elevated levels of SA and SAG in the *put2-1* mutant under SAR (Fig. 8c and d)

Fig. 6. Estimation of free polyamine content in distal leaves following Put infiltration of local leaves. Content of a) Agm, b) Put, c) Spd, and d) Spm was assessed in distal leaves 6 and 24 h after infiltrating lower leaves with either 0 or 30 μ M Put. The values represent the mean of six biological replicates \pm SE. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) among Mock or Put treatment in the WT, *put2-1* mutant, and the *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line, according to three-way ANOVA followed by LSD Fisher's post-hoc test. e) PC analysis of common and uncommon polyamines in WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression lines at 6 and 24 h after infiltrating lower leaves with either 0 or 30 μ M Put. The percentages of total variance represented by PC1 and PC2 are shown in parentheses.

Fig. 7. Estimation of phenolic compounds content in distal leaves following Put infiltration of local leaves. The content of a) salicylic acid (SA), b) SA glycoside (SAG), c) *p*-coumaric acid (pCA), d) ferulic acid (FA), and e) sinapic acid (SiA) was assessed in distal leaves 6 and 24 h after infiltrating lower leaves with either 0 or 30 μ M Put. The values represent the mean of six biological replicates \pm SE. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) among Mock or Put treatment in the WT, *put2-1* mutant, and the *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line, according to three-way ANOVA followed by LSD Fisher's post-hoc test. f) PC analysis of phenolic compounds in WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression lines at 6 and 24 h after infiltrating lower leaves with either 0 or 30 μ M Put. The percentages of total variance represented by PC1 and PC2 are shown in parentheses.

were accompanied by the upregulated expression of *ICS1* and *UGT76B1* genes (Fig. S5a and f). Moreover, a clear correlation was observed between changes in concrete polyamine levels and phenolics (Fig. 8f and h). For instance, Spd showed a negative correlation with SAG at both 6 and 24 hpi, and SA and SAG content were also negatively correlated with Spd, Spm, and tSpm (Fig. 8f and h).

Altogether, our data suggest that higher polyamine accumulation precedes the accumulation of phenolic compounds (SA and hydroxycinnamic acid accumulation) under SAR conditions in the WT and the *35S::PUT2-27*, an aspect that was inverted in the *put2-1* mutant (Fig. 8e and g).

3.10. The SAR-deficient *put2-1* is due to a ROS and stomatal immunity disruption

To further explore systemic responses, we evaluated ROS and stomatal immunity in the WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2-27* lines (Fig. 9). First, superoxide radical ions were detected histochemically in response to local and systemic *Pst* inoculation (Fig. 9a). WT plants increased blue staining, indicating accumulation of superoxide radical ions in their leaves under SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$). Contrarily, the *put2-1* mutant line only accumulated superoxide radical ions after local *Pst* inoculation ($1^{\circ}Mock / 2^{\circ}Pst$), but not under SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$) (Fig. 9a), suggesting that the loss of AtPUT2 function affects ROS accumulation during SAR. This pattern of

(caption on next page)

Fig. 8. Metabolic changes in WT, *put2-1*, and the *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line in SAR. Content of a) Put, b) Spd, c) SA, and d) SAG in systemic leaves under native and SAR induction conditions at 6 and 24 hpi. Values are the mean of three biological replicates \pm SE. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments according to four-way ANOVA followed by LSD Fisher's post-hoc test.

Principal component analysis of free common and uncommon polyamines, and certain phenolic compounds in native (1° Mock / 2° Mock or 1° Mock / 2° Pst) and SAR (1° Pst / 2° Mock or 1° Pst / 2° Pst) conditions of the WT, *put2-1* mutant, and *35S::PUT2-27* overexpression line at e) 6 hpi and g) 24 hpi. The percentages of total variance presented by PC1 and PC2 are shown in parentheses. Pearson correlation matrix of free common and uncommon polyamines and certain phenolic compounds at f) 6 hpi and h) 24 h. Shades of blue indicate increasing positive correlation coefficient; shades of brown indicate increasing negative correlation coefficient. The asterisks represent the significance of the correlation among variables. * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$.

Fig. 9. Histochemical detection of superoxide anion radical in WT and the *put2-1* mutant under SAR, ROS production after *flg22* treatment, and stomatal aperture. a) In situ production of $O_2^{\bullet-}$ was detected in rosette leaves of six-week-old plants by NBT staining 24 hpi in the following conditions: native plant status (1° Mock / 2° Native or 1° Mock / 2° Pst) and SAR (1° Pst / 2° Native or 1° Pst / 2° Pst). The blue color indicates the accumulation of $O_2^{\bullet-}$. Scale bar, 1 cm. b) Time of maximum relative luminescence units (t_{max} RLU) in WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2-27* after treatment with *flg22* in discs of distal leaves derived from plants primed in local leaves with Mock or *Pst*. c) *put2-1* and d) *35S::PUT2-27* compared to WT: luminescence was measured over time after treatment with *flg22* in discs of distal leaves derived from plants primed in local leaves with Mock or *Pst*. The data are presented as mean \pm SE of $n = 20$. Statistical differences among the plant lines were determined using two-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$), followed by a Tukey's HSD test. e) Estimation of stomatal aperture in response to *flg22* treatment in epidermal peels of WT, *put2-1*, and *35S::PUT2-27*. Peels were preincubated for 3 h in opening buffer under light, then treated with 1 μ M *flg22*. Box-and-whisker plots show $n = 100$ stomata. f) Representative images of stomata following *flg22* treatment. Scale bar = 10 μ m.

ROS accumulation aligns with *RBOHD* gene expression, which is highly expressed after local *Pst* inoculation (1° Mock / 2° Pst) but significantly downregulated under SAR (1° Pst / 2° Pst) in the *put2-1* mutant (Fig. S8e).

To further explore the contribution of *AtPUT2* to the ROS response, ROS burst in discs taken from the upper (native leaves) was evaluated under *flg22* elicitation 48 h after priming the lower leaves with Mock or

Pst using the luminol assay (Fig. 9b). Again, different ROS responses were observed among lines. For instance, WT accelerated the ROS production in the *Pst*-primed (t_{\max} ca. 10 min) plants compared to Mock-treated plants (t_{\max} ca. 14 min), confirming that priming accelerates responsiveness to flg22 elicitation (Fig. 9b and c). A similar tendency was observed in the 35S::PUT2-27 line (Fig. 9d). However, the *put2-1* mutant showed similar ROS curves under both *Pst*-primed and Mock-treated plants (Fig. 9b and c). Moreover, the overall curves, calculated by integrating the area under the curve (AUC), were also compared for the three lines (File S2). Although the treatment was not significant, lines showed a clear difference in activating ROS signals, with the *put2-1* mutant exhibiting a substantial compromise in its capacity for ROS accumulation.

The ROS deficiency observed in the *Pst*-primed plants in *put2-1* under SAR and after flg22 elicitation (Fig. 9a and c) suggests that this line may have an alteration in the initial ROS-regulated immune responses occurring in the stomata (Song et al., 2014). To analyze this possibility, we observed stomatal changes in Mock or *Pst*-primed plants by eliciting the distal leaves with flg22 (Fig. 9e and f). Under control conditions, WT and *put2-1* plants showed similar stomatal apertures, whereas the 35S::PUT2-27 line had reduced apertures. After flg22 elicitation, all lines induced stomata closure after 15 min (Fig. 9d). However, whereas the WT and 35S::PUT2-27 lines kept a closed status throughout the experiment, the *put2-1* mutant exhibited significantly larger stomatal apertures at 30 min of flg22 elicitation (Fig. 9e and f). Altogether, our results demonstrate that the *AtPUT2* gene regulates SAR by ROS signaling and stomatal closure in *Arabidopsis*.

4. Discussion

SAR enhances plant immunity by preparing defenses against future infections. Understanding the signaling molecules involved is crucial for deciphering systemic responses and improving sustainable disease resistance in crops. Our study investigated how restricting polyamine transport in *Arabidopsis* polyamine uptake transporter (*put*) mutant lines affects SAR activation. Our findings revealed differences in SAR efficacy among *Arabidopsis put* mutants, suggesting that specific polyamine transporters play a role in systemic immunity. While *put1-1* and *put3-1* mutants demonstrated SAR activation comparable to WT plants, the *put2-1*, *put4-1*, and *put5-1* lines exhibited noticeable SAR deficiencies. Notably, the *put2-1* mutant showed significant susceptibility to reinfection, with higher bacterial titers in SAR-induced plants compared to Mock-infiltrated controls. Further analysis of the *AtPUT2* gene revealed its involvement in broad-spectrum SAR, as the *put2-1* mutant could not limit *B. cinerea* infection following local priming. The dual phenotype observed in *put2-1*, compromised SAR but enhanced basal resistance to *Pst*, highlights a distinctive characteristic of this mutant, suggesting that polyamine transport is key for polyamine-mediated systemic immune responses. Furthermore, the enhanced basal resistance in the *put2-1* mutant remained unaffected by plant age or photoperiod, suggesting that this defense mechanism operates independently of the developmental stage and light-dependent signaling pathways.

Previous studies have shown that mutants defective in lipid biosynthesis and transport (i.e. *sfd1*, *sfd2*, *fad7*, *mgd1*, *dir1*, *mod1*, *lacs2*), the biosynthesis, transport and perception of the mobile signals (i. e. *azi1*, *earl1*, *che*), and epigenetic modifications (i. e. *rsi1*, *ref6*, *fve*, *gstt2*, *pwr*), as well as the lines overexpressing *RRTF1* and *PDLP*, lose SAR induction but maintain basal resistance against *P. syringae* pv. *maculicola* (*Psm*) or to *Pst*, with bacterial titers comparable to those in WT (Maldonado et al., 2002; Nandi et al., 2004; Chaturvedi et al., 2008; Singh et al., 2013; 2023; Carella et al., 2015; Cecchini et al., 2015; Bandy and Nandi, 2018; Chowdhury et al., 2020; Patil and Nandi, 2022; Cao et al., 2024). Conversely, mutants such as *npr1* and *ald1*, and overexpression of *UGT76B1*, which are involved in SA and Pip metabolism, lose both SAR and basal resistance (Cao et al., 1997; Bauer et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2021). Interestingly, *put2-1* shares some features with these mutant lines

but does not fully fit the described phenotypes. Unlike most SAR-deficient mutants, which retain basal resistance, *put2-1* shows enhanced local resistance, as evidenced by reduced bacterial titers.

Although local Put infiltration reduced bacterial titers in WT systemic leaves, mimicking SAR activation, the *put2-1* mutant showed no difference in bacterial titers between Mock and Put-treated plants, suggesting impaired perception or response to Put. Conversely, the 35S::PUT2 lines showed enhanced systemic resistance upon Put treatment. Quantitative analysis confirmed that both WT and 35S::PUT2 lines effectively translocated Put from local to distal tissues, whereas the *put2-1* mutant failed to do so (Fig. 6). These findings support the notion that *AtPUT2* is required for the long-distance transport of Put, which is essential for SAR activation and the regulation of SAR-associated gene expression. A recent study identified a tomato homolog of *PUT2* (phylogenetically clustered with the *Arabidopsis PUT1*, *PUT2*, and *PUT3* genes) as mediating shoot-to-root transport of polyamines (Spd and Put) during salt stress, a process regulated by the HB52 transcription factor (Yang et al., 2025). Additionally, the tomato *PUT3* transporter is involved in polyamine uptake under salt stress (Yang et al., 2024), underscoring the significance of polyamine transport in mediating plant stress responses.

To further understand the SAR-deficient *put2-1* phenotype and the relevance of polyamine regulation, we conducted RNA-seq transcriptomic analysis. Several genes associated with systemic acquired resistance, regulation of defense response, plant-type hypersensitive response, response to hydrogen peroxide, photorespiration, and fatty acid biosynthetic process were deregulated in the *put2-1* mutant under SAR. Specifically, genes related to SA and NHP metabolism, which regulate local immunity and SAR, were altered in *put2-1*. Interestingly, the *ICS1* and *FMO1* genes, crucial for SA and NHP biosynthesis, were highly expressed in the *put2-1* mutant, especially at 24 hpi, when the WT had already reduced their expression. This result indicated that polyamine transport mediated by *AtPUT2* may be crucial for controlling SA and NHP biosynthesis under SAR. None of the known mobile SAR-inducing signals, such as MeSA, AzA, DA, G3P, NHP, and eNAD(P), have been reported to activate systemic SA biosynthesis directly (Kachroo and Kachroo, 2020; Vlot et al., 2021). Interestingly, our results showed a strong link between polyamines and SA biosynthesis because Put infiltration in lower leaves triggered SA accumulation in the upper (systemic) leaves, revealing a novel role for Put or a derived metabolite in regulating systemic SA levels. This extends previous observations that Put stimulates local SA accumulation and induces local and systemic transcriptional reprogramming of genes involved in SAR (Liu et al., 2020). Additional corroboration was that *AtPUT2* was essential for Put-mediated systemic induction of *ICS1*, *PR1*, *SARD4*, *FMO1*, *UGT76B1*, and *NHL10* genes, as this response was largely suppressed in the *put2-1* mutant. Based on our observations, polyamines may act as a key regulatory hub, contributing to the fine-tuning of the balance between activation and attenuation of SAR. While Put functions as an inducer of SAR and defense-related genes (Liu et al., 2020), we observed that higher polyamines, mainly Spm, promote the expression of genes encoding enzymes that inactivate SA and NHP, or their signaling pathways, such as *UGT76B1* and *NIMIN1* (Fig. 4).

UGT76B1, a glycosyltransferase that modifies SA, NHP, and isoleucine, plays a pivotal role in regulating the levels of the active forms that mediate plant immunity (Bauer et al., 2021; Mohnike et al., 2021). *UGT76B1* overexpression increases susceptibility to *Psm* and impairs SAR activation (Bauer et al., 2021). In contrast, the *ugt76b1* mutant exhibits constitutive SAR and accumulates elevated levels of free SA and NHP, indicating impaired inactivation and turnover of these signaling molecules (Bauer et al., 2021; Mohnike et al., 2021). Similarly, we observed decreased *UGT76B1* transcript levels in WT plants from 6 to 24 hpi under SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$), correlating with increased SA levels, which help bolster plant defense. Conversely, increased *UGT76B1* expression in the *put2-1* mutant under SAR conditions likely promotes the glycosylation and subsequent inactivation of SA, NHP, and ILA,

compromising the systemic immune response. Interestingly, we also found that both Spm treatment and *put2-1* under SAR upregulated *UGT76B1* expression in *Arabidopsis*. Moreover, the high Spm levels in the mutant line indicate a clear connection between *UGT76B1* transcript levels and Spm. The *put2-1* mutant also exhibited elevated levels of other higher polyamines, including tSpm, nSpd, and nSpm, which aligned with increased *ADC2*, *SPMS*, and *ACL5* expression. Consistent with these findings, Kim et al. (2019) reported Spm overaccumulation in seeds of the *put2-1* mutant. This accumulation suggests potential defects in polyamine distribution or metabolic regulation within the cell, reinforcing the idea that AtPUT2 is critical for maintaining polyamine homeostasis and proper compartmentalization.

Polyamine supplementation experiments showed that Spd and Spm differently regulate gene expression. Spd treatment induced *NIMIN1* expression in WT plants but not in *put2-1*, while Spm increased *NIMIN1* and *UGT76B1* expression in *put2-1*. *NIMIN1*, a negative regulator of plant immune responses, acts by sequestering the SAR master regulator NPR1 (Mohan et al., 2016). *NIMIN1* was highly expressed in the *put2-1* mutant under native conditions and was further upregulated in response to local priming ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Native$), systemic challenge ($1^{\circ}Mock / 2^{\circ}Pst$), and SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$). Thus, affecting the defense responses in *put2-1*. Overexpression of *NIMIN1* leads to SA intolerance (Mohan et al., 2016), mimicking the *npr1* mutant phenotype characterized by reduced expression of SA-induced *PR* genes, including *PR1*, and impaired SAR. Interestingly, despite the loss of SAR in *put2-1*, *PR1* expression was not repressed, suggesting that a SA-independent pathway might regulate its expression.

ROS are key signaling molecules involved in regulating SAR and stomatal immunity. Previous studies have shown that Put induces *RBOH-D* and *RBOH-F*, which generate apoplastic ROS and contribute to SAR-like responses (Liu et al., 2020). In our study, the *put2-1* mutant line accumulated superoxide radical ions in response to local *Pst* inoculation ($1^{\circ}Mock / 2^{\circ}Pst$) but not under SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$), suggesting a defect in systemic ROS signaling. Various experimental approaches in this study consistently demonstrated that the *put2-1* mutant displays impaired ROS accumulation and systemic signaling. For instance, luminol-based assays revealed that the *put2-1* mutant had weaker ROS signals than the WT and the *35S::PUT2-27* line. Following flg22 elicitation, the *put2-1* mutant showed no differences in ROS dynamics between Mock-treated and *Pst*-primed plants, confirming the compromised systemic response. Moreover, stomatal closure assays revealed that *put2-1* exhibited attenuated responsiveness to flg22 compared to WT, while the *35S::PUT2-27* showed an enhanced response. While stomatal closure mediated by the FLG22 receptor is known to be SA-dependent, polyamines (Put, Spd, and Spm) also significantly contribute to this process by enhancing nitric oxide and ROS production in guard cells. This polyamine response involves the activity of RBOH and amine oxidase enzymes, contributing to stomatal closure (Zheng et al., 2015; Agurla et al., 2018). Put stimulates NO production, thereby promoting stomatal closure (Agurla et al., 2018), a process that may be impaired in *put2-1* due to its reduced Put content under SAR.

SA modulates polyamine metabolism in *Arabidopsis*, increasing Put accumulation via an NPR1-independent but partially MPK6-dependent mechanism, while *Pst* triggers Put accumulation in a SA-dependent manner (Rossi et al., 2021). Although the polyamines-ROS-SA cross-talk has primarily been studied at the biosynthesis level, our findings indicate that AtPUT2-mediated polyamine transport also regulates SA and ROS levels, thereby modulating plant defense and stomatal immunity.

Another key finding of this study was that the *put2-1* mutant exhibited altered expression of genes encoding chloroplast enzymes, mainly related to galactolipid biosynthesis, suggesting a metabolic disorder in this organelle. In addition to its role in photosynthesis, the chloroplast is a crucial organelle involved in synthesizing Pip and precursors of SA, and coordinating plant defense responses (Kachroo et al., 2021). The AtPUT2 transporter has been reported to localize to multiple

intracellular compartments, including the chloroplast and the Golgi apparatus (Li et al., 2013; Fujita and Shinozaki, 2014; Ahmed et al., 2017), with additional localization predictions to the plasma membrane, vacuole, and mitochondria according to the SUBA4 database (Hooper et al., 2017). In chloroplasts, polyamines are key for stabilizing thylakoid structure, post-translational modifications of antenna proteins, and regulating photosynthesis, photoadaptation, and stress responses (Sobieszczuk-Nowicka and Legocka, 2014). Our findings suggest that AtPUT2 may be involved in chloroplast-associated metabolic processes crucial for immune signaling and systemic resistance. However, other previously described roles for polyamines in the chloroplast may also be dependent on their transport.

Although further studies are needed to understand the chloroplast-associated regulation of AtPUT2 in SAR, our assumptions are also supported by the fact that the *put2-1* mutant exhibits a similar phenotype to loss-of-function mutants of genes involved in galactolipid biosynthesis, with compromised SAR, while retaining basal resistance to *Pst* (Maldonado et al., 2002; Nandi et al., 2004; Chaturvedi et al., 2008; Lim et al., 2020). In these mutants, the loss of SAR has been linked to defects in plastid function (Chaturvedi et al., 2008). For example, the *MGDL* gene, which encodes a chloroplast A-type monogalactosyldiacylglycerol synthase required for galactolipid synthesis, plays a role in generating precursors for mobile signals, such as Aza and G3P, which are essential for SAR (Kachroo et al., 2021).

Recently, it has been found that levels of various galactolipids, such as MGDG (18:3, 16:3), MGDG (18:3, 16:2), and MGDG (16:3), which are primary precursors of jasmonic acid (JA), increase in the Spm-deficient *spms* mutant that is *Pst* susceptible and *Bc* resistant (Zhang et al., 2023). Therefore, it is reasonable to suggest that the increased Spm levels in the *put2-1* mutant may also influence galactolipid and JA content as well as the defense responses to pathogens. Moreover, the increased susceptibility to *Bc* in systemic tissues of the *put2-1* mutant could also result from alterations in the ethylene-JA pathway, as recently shown by Zhang et al. (2023) and Peña-Lucio et al. (2025).

Our transcriptomic analysis also revealed that many genes associated with photosynthesis and chloroplast function (Table S3), including those involved in galactolipid synthesis in the chloroplast, such as *MGD1*, *FAD4*, and *FAD7*, were down-regulated in the *put2-1* mutant line (Table 1, Fig. S9). These findings reinforce the evidence that AtPUT2 impacts chloroplast function, and that the SAR deficiency observed in the *put2-1* mutant may also result from disrupted production of galactolipid-derived mobile signals.

5. Conclusion

Our findings reveal the crucial role of the Polyamine Uptake Transporter 2 (*PUT2/LAT4*) in SAR and broad-spectrum SAR establishment in *Arabidopsis*. Fig. 10 shows a model integrating the main findings related to the function of Put and AtPUT2 in systemic responses. AtPUT2 transporter is required for Put transport to systemic tissues, which regulates the expression of essential genes involved in SA and NHP biosynthesis and modulates SA levels. Under SAR ($1^{\circ}Pst / 2^{\circ}Pst$), the *put2-1* mutant exhibits alterations in the expression of SAR-related genes, SA, ROS, and Put content, indicating that the proper timing of accumulation of each actor is crucial for SAR establishment. Particularly, ROS signaling is compromised in the *put2-1* mutant, affecting other key defense responses such as stomatal immunity. The downregulation of crucial genes involved in galactolipid synthesis in the *put2-1* mutant points to future research regarding the importance of polyamine transport in chloroplast-mediated SAR responses. Understanding how polyamine transport mechanisms contribute to plant defense could significantly enhance our understanding of plant stress resilience.

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The Polyamine Uptake Transporter 2 (PUT2) is essential for Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR) establishment in Arabidopsis

Fig. 10. Proposed model of PUT2 involvement in SAR. PUT2 transports putrescine (or its derivatives) from local to distal tissues, promoting the accumulation of SA, Put, and the expression of SAR-related genes. In the *put2-1* mutant, the loss of SAR is associated with altered timing in the accumulation of SA, polyamines, and ROS, as well as in the expression of key SAR-related genes, compared to the wild-type. These changes suggest a disruption in the dynamics of the systemic defense response. Additionally, in SAR, the *put2-1* mutant exhibits increased expression of negative regulators of defense, especially *UGT76B1* and *NIMIN1* genes.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Emmanuel Flores-Hernández: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **María Elisa Gonzalez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Paulina Alvarado-Guitron:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Francisco I. Jasso-Robles:** Resources, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Cesar Ovando-Vázquez:** Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Juan Francisco Jiménez-Bremont:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Sanja Čavar Zeljković:** Investigation. **Markéta Ulbrichová:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nuria De Diego:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Margarita Rodríguez-Kessler:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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